

Bioaccumulation Factor (BAF) of Heavy Metals in Selected Grassy Species in Mejia Thermal Power Plant, West Bengal, India

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Abstract

Pollution from fly ash is one of the principle environmental and public health problems in recent times. Concentrations of toxic metals of Zn, Cu, Pb were determined in the grassy vegetation around Mejia Thermal Power Station, West Bengal, India during November, 2015. Simultaneously the biologically available heavy metals in the fly ash were also estimated to evaluate the bioaccumulation factor (BAF) in the selected grass species. The study reveals that BAF is more in *Typha elephantia* as compared to *Phargmites karka*. The present study is a probable road map for natural bioremediation of fly ash using producer community of the area.

Keywords: Bioaccumulation Factor (BAF), Fly ash, Heavy metals, Grassy species.

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1. Introduction

Fly ash is a budding source of pollution not only for the atmosphere but for the soil, water and other components of the environment (Jena, 2011). The deposition of this air borne pollutant in and around the production source can have negative influences on soil and water bodies because of their granulometric nature, mineral composition and filtration properties (Lokeshappa and Dikshit, 2011).

In recent years, studies on the environmental pollutants have revealed that dusts from industries have a greater ability to develop allergic diseases in humans than natural ones (Obtulowicz et al., 1996). The Mejia Thermal Power Plant, located in the Bankura district produces huge quantum of fly ash for generating 2340 MW of electricity (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Mejia_Thermal_Power_Station). Additionally, they have negative influence on plants mainly on the forestry tree species influencing the biota in and around the thermal power zone (Smółka-Danielowska, 2006; Fulekar and Dave, 1986; Querol et al., 1995; Chirenje and Lena, 1996; Jablonska et al., 2003; Xu et al., 2003; Fytianos et al., 1998). This process is hazardous to the environment if the heavy metal level is not kept under control. The present paper is an attempt to monitor the level of heavy metals in the fly ash dump site as well in the grassy vegetation growing on the fly ash substratum. The Bioaccumulation Factor (BAF) has been used in this paper as proxy to bioaccumulation potential of the selected grassy species.

2. Materials and Methods

The entire network of the present program (carried out during November 2015) consists of three phases namely: i) analyzing the biologically available heavy metals in fly ash substratum, ii) analyzing the heavy metals in the selected grass species (*Typha elephantina* and *Phragmites karka*) that grows naturally and iii) the estimation of Bioaccumulation Factor (BAF) for both the species. The number samples in each cases was 15 (n = 15) and the mean values of 15 samples were expressed in the result section in ppm dry wt. (as unit).

2.1. Analysis of biologically available heavy metals in fly ash

Fly ash samples from the surface (1 cm depth) were scrapped off by using a sterile and acid washed spatula to be sealed immediately in clean polythene bags. The samples were then washed separately with double distilled water and individually oven dried at 105°C for 5 – 6 hours. Following this process, gravel and dirt particles were sieved off from the samples which were then ground to a powder form by using a clean pestle and mortar. The powdered samples were finally stored in clean polythene bags and allowed to re-dry. Analysis of biologically available metals were done by taking 1 gm of each sample and digesting them with 0.5 (N) HCl as per the standard procedure outlined by Malo (1977). The resulting solutions were then set aside in clean containers to be finally aspirated in the flame Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (Perkin Elmer: Model 3030) for the determination of metal concentrations. No detectable trace metals were found in the reagent blank. Analysis of the NIES Sargasso sample was carried out to assure the quality of the data (Table 1).

2.2. Analysis of heavy metals in the selected grass species

To analyze the heavy metal concentration in the grassy vegetation, 10 gm of each sample of the two species were left to dry at 105°C overnight. Each of the dried samples (1 gm on dry weight basis) was then digested in a solution of nitric acid and hydrogen peroxide and hydrochloric acid was later added to it. After completion of the digestion process each of the two samples was analyzed for Zn, Cu and Pb against their standard metal concentrations by AAS (Grimshaw et al., 1989) on a Perkin Elmer Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (Model 3030). The Spectrophotometer had an HGA-500 graphite furnace atomic background corrector and a deuterium background corrector. The results were made more precise by executing blank corrections.

2.3. Computation of Bioaccumulation Factor (BAF)

The Bioaccumulation Factor (BAF) is considered as the equilibrium ratio between the metal concentration in any organ of an organism and its concentration in the ambient media (soil or water).

Thus, $BAF = \frac{\text{Pollutant (selected heavy metals) concentrations in stem or root of selected grassy species (in ppm)}}{\text{pollutant concentration in water/fly ash (in ppm)}}$.

3. Results

It is observed from the Figure 1 that in reclaimed fly ash samples the order of the selected heavy metals is $Zn > Cu > Pb$, whereas in case of dry fly ash samples the order is $Zn > Pb > Cu$.

This picture of heavy metal concentration in fly ash samples synchronizes with the heavy metal levels in the Below Ground Biomass (BGB) and Above Ground Biomass (AGB) of *Typha elephantina* and *Phragmites karka* (Figures 2a and 2b).

It is interesting to note that the Bioaccumulation Factor (BAF) in *Typha elephantina* is greater compared to *Phragmites karka* (Figures 3 and 4), which implies its better potentiality to absorb and accumulates heavy metals from the underlying fly ash samples.

4. Discussion and Conclusion

Nearly 73% of India's total installed power generation capacity is thermal, of which 90% are coal-based thermal power plants, producing nearly 90-100 million tons of fly ash annually as a by-product (Anon, 2000). In India, there are 85 utility Thermal Power Stations, besides the several captive power plants which use bituminous and sub-bituminous coal that contains 30-50% ash generating large volumes of fly ash (Sundaramurthy and Sundaramoorthy, 2014). In a pulverized coal fired thermal power plant about 40-55% ash is produced out of which 20% falls down due to gravity and is removed as bottom ash and the remaining as fly ash.

In Mejia Thermal Power Plant, the generated fly ash is stored in the ponds, where vegetation grows naturally or are planted artificially to restore the ecology of the area. *Phragmites karka* grows in a range of habitats, from swamps to shallow water at the margins of lakes, ponds, in and along streams and ditches and in irrigation canals (Cook, 1996). Also, the species show bioaccumulation of heavy metals in the plant tissues, up taking 35-56% of heavy metals like Cu, Zn, Fe etc, from the substratum (Muhammad Masud et al., 2007). *Typha elephantina* grows in swamps and riversides colonizing a wide variety of wetland habitats and over a geographic range of North Africa, South East Asia, West Asia and China. The roots of the species is highly efficient in absorbing heavy metals present in the surrounding water body, and is recommended by the environmentalists for plantation in the East Kolkata Wetlands, Ramsar site. It is considered as a common grassy species utilized for effluent treatment which can be effective for mitigating the pollution problem in the above mentioned site (Bhattacharya et al., 2012). As many of the heavy metals are toxic in nature, therefore it is essential to monitor the BAF of the species growing on the fly ash dump sites.

The present study reveals the presence of more heavy metals in the roots compared to that in the stem, which can be attributed to the direct contact of the root system with the fly ash basal medium (substratum). The relatively higher BAF in *Typha elephantina* compared to *Phragmytis karka* confirms the efficiency of the tissue system of the species in translocating the heavy metals from the fly ash basal medium to the shoot system. A more detailed seasonal picture of the bioaccumulation pattern of the heavy metals in the selected grassy species (on long term basis) can throw light in the use of these species as potential bio-accumulators of heavy metals or as bio-indicators in the heavy metal infested zone of the Thermal power plants in India.

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Tables and Figures

Table 1: Analysis of reference material (NIES Sargasso sample) for sediments obtained from the National Institute of Environmental Studies, Japan.

Element	Certified value ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$)	Laboratory results ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$)
Zn	28.6	26.2
Cu	14.9	13.7
Pb	2.4	2.9

Figure 1: Analysis of Biologically available heavy metals in fly ash, MTPS.

Source: Datta et al., 2016

Figure 2a: Analysis of heavy metals in the BGB (Below Ground Biomass) of selected grass species of *Typha elephantina* and *Phragmites karka*.

Source: Datta et al., 2016

Figure 2b: Analysis of heavy metals in the AGB (Above Ground Biomass) of selected grass species of *Typha elephantina* and *Phragmites karka*.

Figure 3: Estimation of Bioaccumulation Factor (BAF) for Shoot of selected species.